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DEVELOPMENT OF AN EFFICIENT PASSIVE SEISMIC ISOLATION SYSTEM FOR SUSTAINABLE STRUCTURAL RESILIENCE

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Seismic base isolation systems are important in reducing structural damage by decoupling ground motion from superstructures. However, their inherent limitations in energy dissipation and self-centering, especially under near fault earthquakes, particularly without active control, restrict their overall effectiveness. This research introduces a sustainable modification to the conventional isolation system by integrating a secondary passive damping mechanism inspired by dual-stage automotive shock absorbers. The proposed concept, termed “damping the damper,” seeks to enhance seismic resilience through a multi stage/layered frictional damping strategy while maintaining structural simplicity. The experimental setup comprises a square base representing the Earth’s crust with two superimposed sliding units. The lower unit functions as the primary isolator, and the upper unit represents the proposed secondary isolator. Both units were mounted on low-friction rails inclined 2° toward the center, enabling controlled energy dissipation. Weighted oscillations (1–4.5 kg) were applied to simulate seismic motion, and system performance was assessed based on damping ratio, stabilization time, and self-centering capacity. Results demonstrated a notable improvement in damping ratio (7.6%) over the conventional system (4.67%), accompanied by superior re-centering and reduced residual displacement. The study underscores the potential of multi-stage passive damping systems as an efficient and scalable advancement in seismic protection. This innovation aligns with eco technological principles by promoting sustainable, resilient, and adaptive infrastructure for earthquake-prone regions.

Keywords: Base isolation, Passive damping, Seismic resilience, Energy dissipation